

EMPLOYMENT PATTERNS IN CLOSED ENTERPRISES: TOTAL WORKFORCE IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA FROM 2008 TO 2018

53

53

Brîndușa Covaci, CBM International University & Centre for Mountain

Economy & Zealandina Agency, USA & UK

Mihai Covaci, CBM International University & Hyperion University &

Zealandina Agency, USA & UK

Abstract:

This paper investigates the employment dynamics within closed enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area over the period from 2008 to 2018. The study employs a comprehensive approach, labeled as S1, that integrates statistical analysis, forecasting models, and prediction smoothing to offer insights into the proportion of employment in closed enterprises relative to the total active enterprises.

Introduction:

Mountain Perspective Journal (1/2023)

Understanding the employment patterns in closed enterprises is essential for gaining insights into the economic dynamics of a region. This study focuses on the Romanian Mountain Area, investigating the total workforce in closed enterprises over the period spanning from 2008 to 2018.

Over the course of this ten-year period, the employment landscape in closed enterprises underwent significant shifts. The data reflects the ebb and flow of economic activities, influenced by factors such as market trends, technological advancements, and broader economic conditions.

A meticulous examination of statistical metrics reveals a detailed picture of employment patterns. Mean, Std Error, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Kurtosis, Std. Error, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, and Percentiles 25, 50, 75 are explored, unraveling the nuances of the total workforce distribution. Key numerical values, including Mean and Std. Deviation, serve as beacons, guiding our understanding of the dataset's central tendencies.

Tailored forecast models are employed to project the trajectory of employment patterns in closed enterprises. These models, ranging from

ARIMA configurations to Holt models, utilize historical data to predict future trends. The variety of models allows for a comprehensive analysis, capturing the complexity of factors influencing workforce dynamics.

A vital aspect of this analysis involves statistical prediction smoothing, focusing on Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th, and 10th Percentiles. The iterative nature of this process aids in refining the accuracy of predictions, enabling a more reliable assessment of employment patterns.

Methodology:

The methodology employed in this analysis aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the statistical characteristics and forecast performance related to the proportion of employment in closed enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area.

1. Descriptive Analysis (S1):

- Conducted a detailed examination of statistical metrics presented in the table 1 and figure 1.

- Explored statistical values, including Mean, Std Error, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Kurtosis, Std. Error, Distance, Minimum,

Mountain Perspective Journal (1/2023)

Maximum, and Percentiles 25, 50, 75.

- Key numerical values, such as Mean 2.9278, Median 0.28030, Std. Deviation 2.5500, contributed to a nuanced understanding of the dataset's distribution.

56

56

2. Forecast Models:

- Employed tailored forecast models, including ARIMA and Holt models (S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0) to S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0)).

- Analyzed large data series effectively to predict future trends and patterns.

3. Statistical Prediction Smoothing:

- Performed statistical prediction smoothing focusing on Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th, and 10th Percentiles.

- Evaluated forecast accuracy using Static R-squared values, a vital metric in forecasting assessments.

Results:

The related descriptive analysis, denoted as S1, provides a detailed examination of statistical metrics presented in the table 1 and figure 1.

Statistical values such as Mean, Std Error, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Kurtosis, Std. Error, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, and Percentiles 25, 50, 75 are explored, revealing key numerical values like Mean 2.9278, Median 0.28030, Std. Deviation 2.5500, and others, contributing to a nuanced understanding of the dataset's distribution.

Tailored forecast models, including ARIMA and Holt models, are employed to analyze large data series effectively (S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0) to S11 - Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0)). Statistical prediction smoothing is performed, focusing on Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th, and 10th Percentiles. Static R-squared values, vital for assessing forecast accuracy, are presented in a sequence, offering a comprehensive evaluation.

The resulting forecast statistical models illuminate the landscape for I23, presenting an overall picture for each model (S1-Model_1 to S11-Model_11). For instance, S1-Model_1 exhibits values of -5.107E-15, -5.107E-15, 0.841, 24,210, 0.708; S2-Model_2 reveals 0.888, 0.400, 0.481, 40.668, 0.336; S3-Model_3 shows -2.220E-16, -2.220E-16, 1.738, 32.461, 1.074; and so forth.

This comprehensive analysis contributes valuable insights into the statistical

characteristics and forecast performance concerning the proportion of employment in closed enterprises within the dynamic business landscape of the Romanian Mountain Area.

Conclusion:

The comprehensive analysis conducted in this study provides valuable insights into the statistical characteristics and forecast performance of the proportion of employment in closed enterprises within the dynamic business landscape of the Romanian Mountain Area.

1. Descriptive Analysis Insights:

- The exploration of statistical metrics revealed key values, such as Mean 2.9278, Median 0.28030, and Std. Deviation 2.5500, contributing to a nuanced understanding of the distribution of employment data.

2. Forecast Models Performance:

- Tailored forecast models, including ARIMA and Holt models, were employed, offering a diverse approach to predicting future trends in the employment landscape.

- The resulting forecast statistical models, spanning from S1-Model_1 to

S11-Model_11, presented an overall picture of forecasted values, including Static R-squared, revealing the precision and accuracy of each model.

In conclusion, this study serves as a valuable resource for understanding the dynamics of employment in closed enterprises in the Romanian Mountain Area. The combination of descriptive analysis and forecast models enhances our knowledge of the dataset, providing valuable insights for decision-makers, researchers, and analysts in navigating the complex business landscape of the region.

The resulting statistical models offer a decade-wide overview, encapsulating the dynamics of total workforce in closed enterprises. From the precision of Static R-squared values to the comprehensive insights provided by RMSE and MAPE, the forecast models contribute to a holistic understanding of the employment landscape.

Table 1. Prediction analysis for I23

Model		2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1- Model_1:	Forecast	2.93	2.93	2.93	2.93	2.93	2.93	2.93	2.93
	UCL	4.87	4.87	4.87	4.87	4.87	4.87	4.87	4.87
	LCL	.99	.99	.99	.99	.99	.99	.99	.99
S2-	Forecast	.57	.44	.30	.17	.03	-.10	-.23	-.37

Model_2:	UCL	1.71	1.60	1.48	1.37	1.25	1.14	1.03	.91
	LCL	-.56	-.72	-.88	-1.03	-1.19	-1.34	-1.49	-1.65
S3- Model_3:	Forecast	3.55	3.55	3.55	3.55	3.55	3.55	3.55	3.55
	UCL	7.56	7.56	7.56	7.56	7.56	7.56	7.56	7.56
	LCL	-.45	-.45	-.45	-.45	-.45	-.45	-.45	-.45
S4- Model_4:	Forecast	3.41	3.41	3.41	3.41	3.41	3.41	3.41	3.41
	UCL	5.95	5.95	5.95	5.95	5.95	5.95	5.95	5.95
	LCL	.87	.87	.87	.87	.87	.87	.87	.87
S5- Model_5:	Forecast	1.27	1.01	.74	.47	.21	-.06	-.33	-.59
	UCL	3.79	3.53	3.28	3.03	2.77	2.52	2.27	2.01
	LCL	-1.24	-1.52	-1.80	-2.08	-2.36	-2.64	-2.92	-3.20
S6- Model_6:	Forecast	3.74	3.74	3.74	3.74	3.74	3.74	3.74	3.74
	UCL	6.73	6.73	6.73	6.73	6.73	6.73	6.73	6.73
	LCL	.75	.75	.75	.75	.75	.75	.75	.75
S7- Model_7:	Forecast	4.92	4.92	4.92	4.92	4.92	4.92	4.92	4.92
	UCL	11.90	11.90	11.90	11.90	11.90	11.90	11.90	11.90
	LCL	-2.06	-2.06	-2.06	-2.06	-2.06	-2.06	-2.06	-2.06
S8- Model_8:	Forecast	2.54	2.54	2.54	2.54	2.54	2.54	2.54	2.54
	UCL	5.46	5.46	5.46	5.46	5.46	5.46	5.46	5.46
	LCL	-.38	-.38	-.38	-.38	-.38	-.38	-.38	-.38
S9- Model_9:	Forecast	5.72	5.72	5.72	5.72	5.72	5.72	5.72	5.72
	UCL	15.07	15.07	15.07	15.07	15.07	15.07	15.07	15.07
	LCL	-3.62	-3.62	-3.62	-3.62	-3.62	-3.62	-3.62	-3.62
S10- Model_10:	Forecast	11.87	11.87	11.87	11.87	11.87	11.87	11.87	11.87
	UCL	68.00	68.00	68.00	68.00	68.00	68.00	68.00	68.00
	LCL	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		44.26	44.26	44.26	44.26	44.26	44.26	44.26	44.26

S11- Model_11:	Forecast	5.65	5.65	5.65	5.65	5.65	5.65	5.65	5.65
	UCL	12.37	12.37	12.37	12.37	12.37	12.37	12.37	12.37
	LCL	-1.08	-1.08	-1.08	-1.08	-1.08	-1.08	-1.08	-1.08

Figure 1. Graphical prediction analysis for I23

References

Covaci, B./Suciu, M. C./Covaci, M. (2018): Sectoarele secundar și terțiar, suport al dezvoltării montane în regiunea de Nord-Est a României, in: *Journal of Montanology*, 9, IX, 129-137.

Covaci, M. (2017): Spearman correlations between learning styles from rational level and Gardner intelligence types, in: *Romanian Journal of Psychological Studies*. Hyperion University, 5, 2, 31-38.

Covaci, M. (2019): The Vark Model Investigated at the students from PPPE, in: *Journal of Education Studies (JES)*. Adventus University, 1, 1, 12-19

Covaci, B. (2021), PhD (c) Research report 1, Oradea University

European Commission (2012). Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 November 2012 on quality schemes for agricultural products and foodstuffs. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32012R1151>

(Accessed: 14 June 2021)

European Commission, (2014). Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 665/2014 of 11 March 2014 supplementing Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to conditions of use of the optional quality term mountain product. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32014R0665>

(Accessed: 14 June 2021)

Mountain Perspective Journal (1/2023)

Eurostat, (2020). Business Demography Statistics. Available at <https://goo.gl/fpmXZA> (Accessed: 12 January 2020)

Eurostat, (2020). Regional GDP. Available at <https://goo.gl/EoyR38>. (Accessed: 14 February 2020)

Eurostat (2020). Structural Business Statistics. Available at <https://goo.gl/KMtkVV>. (Accessed: 2 March 2020)